

Diabase fine waste for its use in cement-based mortar: Technical remarks, characterization and benefits for the industry

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ABSTRACT

The dimension stone industry generates substantial amounts of moist fine waste during stone processing, raising environmental, economic, and health concerns regarding its accumulation. Addressing the management of this waste is a critical priority. One potential solution is to repurpose stone fine waste as a cost-effective raw material in cement-based mortars. This study focuses on fine waste derived from the diabase transformation process, a medium-grained subvolcanic rock valued for its properties and colour. Despite its potential, diabase fine waste (DFW) remains underexplored as a raw material for mortar production. The authors' analysis revealed that this industrial waste is more complex than initially understood, containing wood fibres (1 %) and slate rock (20 %). This study offers a characterization of DFW to assess its quality control parameters under practical application conditions. Based on its size distribution and fineness modulus, DFW qualifies as a filler material, with particle shape and texture well-suited for mortar applications. The density of DFW ($2964 \pm 46 \text{ kg/m}^3$) is similar to some types of cement, enabling mass-based replacement without altering the mortar's volume. Additionally, DFW exhibits a higher specific surface area ($2.3401 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) than some cements but demonstrates lower water absorption than granite fine waste. DFW's mineralogical and chemical properties are compatible with cement formulations, and it exhibits some pozzolanic activity, despite being considered a non-inert mineral admixture. These findings suggest that DFW has significant potential as a filler material in mortar production. However, further research is needed to ensure the homogeneity of DFW for industrial applications.

1. Introduction

The dimension stone industry produces large amounts of waste, which are present mainly in two forms: solids (generated mainly during the extraction process in quarries) and moist fine powder or sludge (produced mainly during the transformation process: cutting, smoothing and polishing stages). The latter is the most predominant form resulting during all the processing stages at the transformation zones that are produced above stocking capacity [1]. This fine waste may also contain other products derived from the transformation process. As a result, its composition may vary somewhat from that of the source rock and depend on the industrial stage in which it is generated [2, 3]. The increased accumulation of this type of waste at the dumping sites daily causes serious environmental, such as being a source of pollution in some cases and, in others, economic costs due to transport and disposal

to landfills. Solutions to managing this waste are a priority for the dimension stone industry. Recycling this waste in manufacturing beneficial and sustainable products can be considered one of them.

Although the construction sector consumes natural resources and energy, it plays an important role in its capacity to absorb other industries' waste and by-products [4]. Many researchers are interested in using stone waste fines as the cheapest alternative material in manufacturing added-value products, such as cement-based mortar.

A typical mortar mix consists of three primary components: binder (usually cement), sand and water. Stone waste fines, due to their fineness, can satisfactorily fulfil the requirements to serve as fine aggregate or filler (inert mineral admixtures) to reduce the consumption of sand or cement in mortars [5].

There are many types of stone waste fines. They can come from different stones such as limestone, marble, granite, basalt or diabase.

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Diabase stone is very much appreciated due to its dark colour and mechanical properties. Diabase or dolerite is an intrusive igneous rock with distinctive characteristics that differentiate it from other common igneous rocks such as granite and basalt. It is a fine to medium-grained subvolcanic rock with a composition similar to basalt, although it may exhibit pozzolanic activity [6]. This rock is widely distributed on all five continents. Some of the most important reserves are found in countries such as Australia [7], South Africa [8], India [9], Brazil [10]. In American countries such as Uruguay, diabase production corresponds to 40 % of the country's dimension stone production [11]. In Europe, diabase reserves are present from North (United Kingdom, Ireland or Scandinavian countries) to South (Spain) and from West (Germany) to East (Russia) [12–16]. In fact, Sweden is known worldwide for the quality of its diabase. On the other hand, diabase is one of the stones known commercially as black granite (basalt, diabase, gabbro, diorite and anorthosite), although its chemical and mineralogical compositions differ from those of true granites (ASTM C119 [17]). Based on the Black Granite Market Report 2024 (Global Edition) [18], the diabase market (considered as absolute black granite) can be estimated at 103371 million USD in 2024 and will expand from 2024 to 2031. The above data show that a large amount of material has to be produced to meet the demand. Therefore, a large amount of diabase waste fines (DFW) is and will be generated since it is estimated to be over 30 % of the volume of the sawn block, as in the case of granite [19].

DFW has not been explored for its potential as a raw material in mortar production. In contrast, some properties of granite waste fines (GFW) and basalt waste fines (BFW), both igneous rocks, from the dimension stone industry and other industries (crushing quarry and asphalt mixer plant) have been examined for use as fine aggregate or filler.

Regarding its physical properties, GFW can exhibit a particle size distribution similar to that of fine aggregate [20] or filler [1]. Particle size distributions typical of filler were more documented for BFW [21–23]. Properties such as shape and texture were evaluated using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) [22, 24]. According to Laibao et al. [24], BWF negatively affects the workability of cement paste due to its sharp-edged grains and rough surface. GFW particles are more angular and prismatic than the rounder cement particles [25].

The specific surface area of GFW and BFW, when used as a replacement of fine aggregate or filler, can impact different properties of mortars. Sharma and Vyas [26] reported that using granite waste fines as fine aggregate increases the water-cement ratio, as the finer particles increase the surface area, requiring more water to achieve the desired flow. However, increasing the fineness of BFW when it is used as filler to replace cement only slightly influences the hydration kinetics and mechanical properties of mortar [22].

In general, the mineralogical composition of GFW and BFW studied aligns with the mineralogy typically associated with fresh granite (quartz, feldspars, and micaceous components) [27] and basalt (plagioclase, pyroxenes, and amphiboles) [28]. The chemical composition of GFW and BFW predominantly contains SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 , with high equivalent Na_2O content. Due to their chemical composition and fine particle size, these wastes may exhibit pozzolanic activity. Despite this, most studies have focused on using GFW and BFW as fine aggregates or fillers. However, some researchers have also evaluated GFW and BWF waste fines to be used as pozzolans (non-inert mineral admixtures) in mortars.

Medina et al. [29] studied the pozzolanic activity of GFW in a pozzolan/ $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ system. They reported that the pozzolanic activity was similar to that of other additions (copper and SiMn slag), but lower than that found in pozzolans, such as silica fume, which are traditionally used in cement. Furthermore, Medina et al. [30] determined the pozzolanic activity of GFW by measuring the activity index. The strength activity index (SAI) at 28 days in mortars was higher than the 75 % required by standards ASTM C618 [31] for fly ash or natural pozzolans and 70 % EN 450–1 [32] for fly ash for cement replacement ratios of 20 % y 25 %

respectively. Ramos et al. [25] used the Frattini test described in standard EN 196–5 [33] to evaluate the pozzolanicity of GFW. The existence of pozzolanic activity was confirmed. In contrast, Ramadji et al. [34] reported that GFW does not exhibit pozzolanic activity. Both the Frattini test and the modified Chapelle test were used. A study showed that BFW from crushing plants had potential pozzolan activities. The strength activity index at 7 and 28 days was similar to that of fly ash, according to the requirements of ASTM C618 [31] for fly ash [24].

Due to the scarcity of studies on using stone waste fines from diabase as a replacement of fine aggregate or cement in mortars, the present research endeavours to address this gap by pioneering the characterization of DFW. Furthermore, many of the publications dealing with the utilization of stone waste fines, with some variability, provide limited information on the characteristics of these materials. Consequently, the more widespread application of the technical and scientific results is limited. Therefore, this work includes a more refined characterization of DFW under study, to disclose some quality control parameters under real application conditions, considering the typology of stone waste, manufacturing process conditions and management. A more detailed analysis paves the way for determining the most appropriate use of this new raw material in mortar, such as fine aggregate, filler, or pozzolans, before its use in mortar.

2. Materials and methods

The characteristics of a fine aggregate or filler affect the properties of mortar differently; therefore, it was considered appropriate to divide the DFW characterization into four categories based on physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties and pozzolanic activity.

2.1. Collection and sample preparation

DFW evaluated in this investigation was sourced from an ornamental rock factory located in Villar del Rey, Badajoz ($39^\circ 07' 57'' \text{ N}$; $6^\circ 50' 52'' \text{ W}$), a province within Extremadura, one of Spain's autonomous regions. This factory produces two varieties of dimension diabase with the commercial names of *Granito Negro Encina* y *Granito Negro Villar*. Both dimension diabase varieties are composed of plagioclase, pyroxene, amphibole and opaque minerals. The factory is equipped with the extraction and transformation process, generating moist DFW from both processes. Moist DFW was collected from the transformation process during the squaring stage. The parallelepiped blocks of raw stone are subjected to squaring operations by cutting. Blocks of different thicknesses and sizes are then subjected to the disc-cutting, smoothing and polishing stages (Fig. 1).

Approximately 60 kg of moist DFW were collected from an earthen settling basin. Due to its nature, moist DFW tends to clump together, resulting in non-uniform distribution within the mix. Initially, the moist DFW had a degree of moisture around 40 %, and the moist DFW was subjected to a thorough drying process lasting 48 h at 100° C in a laboratory oven. Subsequently, the dried DFW underwent hammering and hand-milling to eliminate lumps, yielding DFW. DFW was further dried in an oven for 24 h at 100° C until reaching a constant weight before characterization to ensure the removal of all residual moisture.

2.2. Physical characterization

2.2.1. Particle size distribution and fineness modulus

There are many reasons for analysing particle size distribution or grading of DFW. The particle size distribution of aggregates and filler significantly affects several characteristics of mortar, including packing density, void content, and, consequently, workability, segregation, durability, and other relevant properties. However, the most important reason for this study was to analyse whether DFW was more appropriate as a fine aggregate or filler material.

The DFW's particle size distributions were analysed: (1) by dry

Fig. 1. Location and dimension diabase manufacturing process at the factory: Villar del Rey Natural Stones S.L.

sieving manually in accordance with EN 13139 [35] and EN 933-2 [36] and (2) by wet sieving manually.

A 300 g sample was considered, and three specimens of DFW were analysed manually by dry sieving. The manual sieving was performed on three specimens of DFW using sieve sizes ranging from 5 mm to 0.063 mm, with intermediate sizes of 4 mm, 1.7 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.25 mm. The particles retained in the sieves, which appeared to be agglomerated, were carefully separated manually. At this initial stage, it became evident that DFW contained not only diabase waste but also fragments of other rocks and industrial materials, highlighting the need for further qualitative and quantitative assessments.

A particle size distribution analysis was conducted within the size range of 475 μm to 25 μm (by wet sieving) to gain a more comprehensive understanding of DFW. Firstly, the sample underwent wet sieving to separate DFW into distinct particle fractions: over 475 μm , 475–212 μm , 212–106 μm , 106–53 μm , 53–25 μm and under 25 μm . Subsequently, the separated particle fractions were dried in an oven at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The fineness modulus was calculated by adding the total percentage of the sample of DFW retained on each of a specified series of sieves during dry sieving and then dividing the sum by 100.

2.2.2. Shape, texture and colour

The DFW's particle shape and texture were comprehensively characterised due to its importance in forming a stronger physical bond with the cement paste. The shape, texture and colour of diabase fine waste particles were evaluated by visual analysis. A NIKON SMZZ645 stereomicroscope and a MOTICAM 10 MP digital camera were utilized. The particles' shape and texture were classified in accordance with the categorization outlined in BS: 812-1 [37]. The reference terms utilized to define the particle's shape were rounded, irregular, angular, and flaky. The particles' texture was classified as rough or smooth [38]. The particle's colour was determined using the Munsell colour system, per the specifications prepared by the Rock-Color Chart Committee [39].

2.2.3. Specific density and specific surface

The DFW's specific density and specific surface, as collected and of

particle fractions > 475 μm , 212–106 μm , and < 25 μm obtained from particle size distribution by wet sieving, were evaluated.

DFW's specific density was determined using a QUANTA CHROME model SPY-3 helium pycnometer using three measurements. A BET surface area analyser was employed to measure the specific surface of DFW, offering a comprehensive analysis of fineness that complemented the tests of particle size distribution and fineness modulus. The specific surface value was found by measuring N_2 adsorption isotherms on a Micrometrics ASAP 2000 analyser. A sample weight of around 0.3 g was used.

2.2.4. Loose bulk density and water absorption

Knowledge of the loose bulk density is of interest, especially in production control and transport management, especially if DFW is used as a raw material for mortar. In accordance with EN 1097-3 [40], the loose bulk density was tested using three specimens of DFW. Each specimen weighed 150 % of the amount needed to fill the 1 L calibrated container.

The total water absorption of DFW, as it was collected, was evaluated using an adaptation of the procedure described in EN 1097-6 [41]. A test portion of DFW was saturated with water for 24 h. Then, a test specimen was taken, and its surface was dried with a cloth until a saturated dry surface condition was reached [42]. Subsequently, the specimen was weighed, and the obtained value was recorded as a mass of the saturated and surface-dried dust in the air (Fig. 2). Repetitions are carried out until three values with relative variations from the mean of less than 10 % are obtained. Then, the test was carried out with three specimens of granite fine waste to compare results with the same method.

2.3. Mineral characterization

2.3.1. Mineralogical composition

The characteristics of the fresh rock primarily determine the quality of stone waste fines. XRD analyses were conducted to check whether the internal components of DFW align with the mineralogy of the fresh

Fig. 2. Water absorption test: (a) immersion for 24 h of test portion; (b) test portion after decanting most of the water covering it; (c) test specimen < 50 g; (d) dried test specimen with soft absorbent cloth; (e) test specimen with saturated and surface-dried particle density; (f) test specimen to be weighed and dried in a ventilated oven at until it has reached a constant mass.

diabase rock from the quarry. A PANALYTICAL XPRT-PRO diffractometer system was utilized, equipped with a Cu K α radiation X-ray source ($\lambda=1.542 \text{ \AA}$). The scan step size was 0.033° , ranging from 5° to 70° (2θ), with an equivalent collection time of 150 s per step. The X-ray tube operated at a fixed voltage of 40 kV and a current of 35 mA. This X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a DFW sample collected in a separate phase, including magnetic and non-magnetic components (separation with a manual Nd magnet) and fractions of different sizes. This comprehensive approach was adopted to increase the accuracy and depth of the results obtained. For phase identification, X'PERT PLUS software and a PDF4 database were employed. This database facilitated the identification of various crystalline phases present in the sample based on their X-ray powder diffraction patterns.

2.3.2. Mineralogical calibration

After confirming that the waste also contained traces of slate (Section 3.1), a regional rock found near the diabase quarry, it became necessary to quantify its proportion in DFW. To achieve this, a mineralogical calibration was conducted by comparing XRD patterns to determine the percentage of slate in the DFW under study.

Initially, fresh rock samples of diabase and slate were collected. They

were manually broken-down using hammers, followed by grinding in a mill and an agate mortar. A 2 g sample of fresh diabase powder, fresh slate powder, and slate–diabase mixtures containing slate proportions of 10 %, 20 %, 30 %, 40 %, 50 %, 60 %, 70 %, 80 %, and 90 % were prepared and analysed using XRD and a digital scanning EPSON PERFECTION V750 PRO. Fig. 3 shows slate–diabase fresh powder and slate–diabase mixtures (Fig. 3a) and DFW and DFW < 25 μm versus slate–diabase mixtures (Fig. 3b).

2.4. Chemical characterization

The chemical composition of DFW was determined using wavelength dispersive XRF with a BRUKER S4 Pioneer instrument operating at 4 kV. The analysis was performed exclusively on powdered samples dried to constant weight and pressed for examination using internal calibration in standardless mode. Beyond identifying the primary compositional trends, the XRF analysis provides critical insights into safety considerations and environmental impact.

Fig. 3. (a) Slate–diabase fresh powder and slate–diabase mixtures; (b) DFW and DFW < 25 μm versus slate–diabase mixtures.

2.5. Evaluation of pozzolanic activity

Understanding the degree of DFW's pozzolanic activity was interesting, as well as determining whether DFW could be used as a pozzolan instead of a filler. The literature reports a wide range of direct and indirect test methods for assessing pozzolanic activity. SAI is the most widely used indirect approach. This test method was used to determine the actual contribution of microstructure densification resulting from the pozzolanic activity of DFW. The DRX technique directly quantifies the consumption of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in hydrated samples [43]. This test method was employed to examine the changes over time in the mineralogical and hydrated phases of mortar with DFW. Moreover, visual analyses were employed to explore the macro and microstructure of mortar with DFW, which offered a comprehensive analysis that complemented the other techniques.

2.5.1. Strength activity index

To determine SAI, two sets of test specimens were made using a standard mortar mix design, one with 100 % cement (reference sample) and the other with a cement–pozzolan blend. Both specimens were examined for compressive strength after 7, 28 and 90 days of curing. The applicable standard was EN 450–1 [32], which compares the compressive strength of mortar mix with pozzolan, replacing 25 % of the cement binder with the reference mix. SAI is a measure of the pozzolanic material's impact, and it was calculated using Eq. (1):

$$\text{SAI} = (\sigma_1/\sigma_2) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

σ_1 and σ_2 denote the compressive strengths of the sample with pozzolan replacement and the control sample, respectively.

The reference mortar was prepared by mixing 1350 g of sand, 450 g of cement and 225 ml of water in a mixer according to EN 196–1 [44]. The specimens prepared were de-moulded after 24 h. All specimens were cured at 20 °C and 95 % of relative humidity following EN 12390–2 [45].

To analyze the influence of the particle size on SAI, DFW and DFW < 63 μm fractions were evaluated.

2.5.2. Changes in hydrated phases in mortar with DFW

To analyse the pozzolanic activity of DFW through the XRD technique, samples of mortar with DFW at the ages of 7, 28, and 90 days were evaluated. The samples were collected from the SAI test. The subsequent manual hammering processes were employed to break down the samples, followed by sieving isolate powder particles under 106 μm . This preparation facilitated a more detailed analysis of information binder products. These meticulously chosen fractions underwent XRD analysis, outlined in Section 2.3.1, to ensure precise phase identification. This scrupulous approach highlights the critical role of accurate phase selection in comprehensively assessing DFW's impact on mortar properties.

2.5.3. Changes in macro and microstructure in mortar with DFW

The visual analysis incorporates various techniques, including digital camera acquisition and stereomicroscopy techniques, utilizing the equipment described in section 4.1.2. The samples were collected from SAI test and were dried (above 100 °C). These chosen samples underwent visual analysis at 7, 28 and 90 days of curing age. Stereomicroscope observations of patterns through high-scale images were carried out to understand the initial microstructural characteristics of the mortar with DFW.

3. Results

3.1. Physical characterization

Particle sizes greater than 0.25 mm pass more than 90 % of three specimens of DFW evaluated. The mean percentages by weight of DFW

passing through the sieve 0.25 mm, 0.125 mm and 0.063 mm are 93.6 % \pm 7.5, 82.3 % \pm 14, and 73.5 % \pm 13.4, respectively (Table 1). The material presents a narrow particle size distribution. The dominant fractions are below 0.063 mm. DFW is poorly graded and characterized by slight variations in size. It contains DFW particles that are almost of the same size. This can limit the solid structure of mortar, but it can be compensated by natural aggregate grading if a partial replacement is foreseen; this is not the case when it is used as a replacement of cement.

The high range values in the 0.125 mm and 0.063 mm fractions indicated that the dry sieving was not the most suitable to analyse the DFW's particle size distributions especially in the smaller particle size. Therefore, a wet sieving was carried out. The particle size distribution analysis within the size range of 475 μm to 25 μm (by wet sieving) enabled the identification of additional industrial fibre contamination of DFW. DFW comprises fine particles from the source stone and fibres (Table 2). The presence of fibres (~1 wt%) is mainly observed in the fractions of DFW, over 475 μm , 212 μm , and 106 mm.

Stereomicroscope observations reveal that DFW comprises fine particles from the source stone, fibres, and other mixtures. Moreover, different particle shapes and surface textures are observed as a function of particle fraction (Fig. 4). If a visual classification is made according to their degrees of roundness as set out in BS: 812–1, DFW particles present flaky and irregular particles in the fraction > 475 μm (Fig. 4a). In the 475–212 μm and 212–106 μm fractions, DFW particles show mainly irregular shapes, although flaky particles are also observed (Fig. 4b and c). An irregular shape dominates in the rest of the fractions of DFW, 106–53 μm and 53–25 μm (Fig. 4d and e). On the other hand, DFW exhibits mainly rough texture in the fraction > 106 μm .

The different colours observed in DFW particles are related to areas with varying mineralogical compositions, as indicated by the XRD analysis. DFW presents three main colours: some are dark grey particles (N3), others are orange (10YR 6/6), and a few display white colour (N9).

The results of specific density (together with the range) and specific surface area of the DFW and DFW fractions > 475 μm , 212–106 μm , and < 25 μm (without fibres) are shown in Table 2. A decanting process was carried out to separate the fibres.

All specific density values are of the same order of magnitude regardless of the type of fraction evaluated. It is highlighted that DFW fractions < 25 μm show the highest value of specific density. A slight increase of specific density with increasing fraction size is observed. The specific gravity of granular material does not measure its quality [46]. Its specific density depends on the specific density of the minerals of which they are composed and on the volume of voids.

The results of the specific surface are vital for assessing the potential of DFW as a filler. The specific surface of DFW fractions without fibre shows a different order of magnitude. The values of DFW fractions over 25 μm are more typical of aggregates, whereas fractions under 25 μm are more typical of mineral admixtures. On the other hand, as collected, the DFW's specific surface is higher than that over 45 μm and similar to that of the 475–212 μm fraction.

Despite its interest, the literature reports few data concerning mortars containing stone fine waste. Knowing the value of loose bulk density is useful. Mortar mixes are generally dosed by volume. Moreover, as

Table 1
Particle size distribution of DFW by dry sieving.

No. Sieve	Pass wt%		
	Specimen 1°	Specimen 2°	Specimen 3°
5 mm	100	100	100
4 mm	100	100	99
1.7 mm	99	99	97
1 mm	98	98	95
0.5 mm	97	97	92
0.25 mm	96	96	89
0.125 mm	85	88	74
0.063 mm	80.7	72.6	67.3

Table 2
Particle size distribution of DFW by wet sieving. Fiber fractions inside plastic bags.

No. Sieve (μm)	Retained wt., %	Fibre wt. in each fraction, %	Fibre wt. in total sample, %	Pictures
475	2.6	10.6	0.3	
212	1.0	27.9	0.3	
106	2.2	6.1	0.1	
53	12.6	-	-	-
25	22.0	-	-	-
< 25	59.5	-	-	-
Total fibre wt., %	-	-	0.7	-

mentioned in Section 2, it is important for DFW's production control and transport management. The loose bulk density of the diabase was 1085 kg/m³ (Table 3).

As described in section 4.1.4, the procedure from EN 1097-6 [41] has been adapted to evaluate the total water absorption of DFW [42]. The total water absorption of GFW with filler size was also evaluated for comparison purposes. The results show that DFW has lower absorption than the GFW evaluated, although of the same order of magnitude (Fig. 5).

3.2. Mineral characterization

The minerals present in DFW consisted of tectosilicates such as feldspars (plagioclase-solid solution of two-end members, albite (NaAl-Si₃O₈) and anorthite CaAl₂Si₂O₈) and amphiboles, e.g. magnesiohornblende ((Ca₂[Mg₄(Al,Fe³⁺)](Si₇Al)O₂₂(OH)₂)). Phyllosilicates, e.g. clinocllore (Al₂(Si₂O₅)(OH)₄), stilpnomelane K₅(Fe,Mg)₄₈[Si₆₃Al₉O₁₆₈(OH)₄₈.12H₂O and phlogopite KMg₃AlSi₃O₁₀(F,OH)₂, pyroxene-type inosilicates, e.g. augite ((Ca, Na)(Mg,Fe,Al)(Si,Al)(Si,Al)₂O₆), and tectosilicates, e.g. quartz (SiO₂), are also present (Fig. 6).

The XRD patterns presented in Fig. 6 also indicate that particle fraction < 25 μm of DFW has a mineralogical composition similar to the overall DFW. Magnetic and paramagnetic minerals in the mineralogical composition of DFW are also observed. Clinocllore (Mg,Fe)₅Al(Si₃Al)O₁₀(OH)₈, magnesiohornblende ((Ca₂[Mg₄(Al,Fe³⁺)](Si₇Al)O₂₂(OH)₂))

Table 3
Specific density, specific surface and loose bulk density of DFW and DFW fractions.

Fraction (μm)	Specific density (kg/m ³)	Specific surface (m ² /g)	Loose bulk density (kg/m ³)
DFW	2964 ± 46	2.3401	1085
> 475	2953 ± 44	0.6794	-
475–212	-	-	-
212–106	2963 ± 74	0.9612	-
106–53	-	-	-
53–25	-	-	-
< 25	3051 ± 41	3.4753	-

Fig. 4. Stereomicroscope of DFW: (a) over 475 μm fraction; (b) 475–212 μm fraction; (c) 212–106 μm fraction; (d) 106–53 μm fraction; (e) 53–25 μm fraction. Black bar 1 mm.

Fig. 5. Total water absorption of stone fine wastes.

and ilmenite (FeTiO_3) dominate, as well as augite ($(\text{Ca}, \text{Na})(\text{Mg}, \text{Fe}, \text{Al})(\text{Si}, \text{Al})(\text{Si}, \text{Al})_2\text{O}_6$), and stilpnomelane $\text{K}_5(\text{Fe}, \text{Mg})_{48}[\text{Si}_{63}\text{Al}_9]\text{O}_{168}(\text{OH})_{48} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The XRD patterns also indicate no significant amorphous content in the DFW, usually recognized by broad reflections in the $15\text{--}35^\circ 2\theta$ range.

Considering that the DFW under study is a mixture of diabase and slate waste, the results obtained show that this DFW contains approximately 10–20 % of slate particles but closer to the latter value (Fig. 7). These data also agree with the composition evaluated by X-ray

fluorescence (XRF). As described in section 4.2.2, quantification was based on pattern comparison. The main minerals taken as reference were: (1) from diabase fresh powder (D), the plagioclase usually recognized by broad reflections in the $28^\circ 2\theta$ range and (2) from slate fresh powder (S), the quartz usually recognized by broad reflections in the $26.65^\circ 2\theta$ range. Other minerals used for reference were the amphibole (typical mineral of diabase) and illite (typical mineral of slate).

On the other hand, the colour of DFW under study and DFW $< 25 \mu\text{m}$ fraction is between the colour of the samples resulting from a mix of 80 % of D with 20 % of S and 90 % of D with 10 % of S (Fig. 3b). This finding establishes that there is a traceability between the mineralogical composition of DFW and its colour, and therefore, can allow for the control of DFW composition by visual inspection.

3.3. Chemical characterization

The chemical composition of DFW and DFW $< 25 \mu\text{m}$ fraction is presented in Table 4. As expected, DFW and DFW $< 25 \mu\text{m}$ fractions present a similar chemical composition to that of the mineralogical composition. The majority of components, silica (SiO_2), alumina (Al_2O_3) and iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), were found together with other oxides such as calcium oxide (CaO), sodium oxide (Na_2O), magnesium oxide (MgO), and titanium dioxide (TiO_2). The mass fractions of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 , dominate, which is typical for diabase fresh rock, and are about 70 %. The LOI of DFW is similar to that of DFW $< 25 \mu\text{m}$ fraction, which may indicate a similar presence of clay minerals. It is known that slate has water and other volatiles constituents.

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of DFW and different fractions.

Fig. 7. XRD pattern: (a). D, S and D-S mixtures; (b) DP-SP mixtures and DFW.

Table 4

Chemical composition of DFW and DFW < 25 μm by XRF.

Oxides	Na ₂ O	MgO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	MnO	Fe ₂ O ₃	LOI
DFW	8.5	3.7	13.9	44.2	1.3	0.1	0.5	7.1	2.0	0.2	12.5	2.6
DFW < 25 μm	6.5	3.8	15.0	42.1	1.3	0.1	0.6	7.1	2.3	0.2	13.9	2.4

3.4. Evaluation of pozzolanicity

SAI at 7, 28, and 90 days for the mortar mixes containing 25 % DFW (MDFW) and the DFW fraction under 63 μm (MDFW < 63 μm), as determined in Eq. (1), is shown in Fig. 8a. In general, SAI, regardless of the type of fraction, is higher than 70 % at 28 days. The mortar mix with DFW shows similar SAI at 28 and 90 days of age. However, an increase of SAI with increasing age in MDFW < 63 μm is observed (77 %). The difference between the two mortars is the presence of fibres in the mortar with DFW, and the maximum particle size is larger.

On the other hand, the increase in compressive strength from 7 days

to 28 days of MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm is higher than that of the reference mortar mix (REFM). However, the increase in compressive strength from 28 days to 90 days of MDFW is similar to that of REFM. Fig. 8b illustrates the compressive strength values obtained in all mortar mixes, as well as the rate of increase in compressive strength at various time intervals.

The XRD patterns for mortar mixes from 7 to 90 days and XRD main diagnostic phase peaks are presented in Fig. 9 and Table 5. For REFM (Fig. 9a) at 7 days, apart from quartz, which is mainly associated with sand incorporation, the prominent peak is portlandite (Ca(OH)₂). Additionally, the diffraction patterns for REFM reveal the presence of

Fig. 8. Mortar mixes with DFW and DFW < 63 μm: (a) SAI at 7, 28 and 90 days; (b) compressive strength and increase rate at 7, 28 and 90 days.

cowlesite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{10} \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$). C-S-H and ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12} \cdot 27 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) were also identified. After 28 and 90 days, the XRD pattern for the reference mortar mix confirms the presence of the same phases, except cowlesite, whose peaks are gone. The differences between 28 days and 90 days are limited to (1) the presence of calcite (CaCO_3) at 90 days due to carbonation and (2) the more intense quartz peaks at 90 days due to the higher presence of sand during sample preparation. Sand separates worse from the paste at 90 days. For MDFW (Fig. 9b) at 7 days, C-S-H and ettringite are also identified, although the mortar mix exhibits reduced levels of portlandite and ettringite compared to REF. At 28 and 90 days, the XRD patterns are similar. The difference between 28 days and 90 days is limited to the lower presence of portlandite and the higher presence of calcite at 90 days. The calcite peaks indicate that the mortar mix has undergone carbonation at 90 days. Moreover, MDFW shows a higher presence of calcite than REF. For MDFW < 63 μm (Fig. 9c) at 7 days, C-S-H and ettringite are also identified, although the mortar mix shows more reduced levels of portlandite and ettringite than REF. At 28 and 90 days, the XRD pattern

Table 5
Hydrated and carbonated phases XRD of mortar mixes.

Compound name	Reference code	Chemical formula	REFM score	MDFW score	MDFW < 63 μm score
Portlandite, syn	00-044-1481	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	34	34	34
Calcium silicate hydrates	00-033-0306	C-H-S	50	50	50
Ettringite, syn	00-041-1451	$\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	60	60	60
Calcite, syn	00-005-0586	CaCO_3	43	29.5	48.5

for reference mortar mix confirms the presence of the same phases and the lower presence of portlandite and calcite at 90 days. The presence of calcite peaks indicates that the mortar mix has undergone carbonation at 90 days, but MDFW shows a similar presence of calcite than REF. These findings suggest that the main difference in the early curing

Fig. 9. XRD pattern of REF, MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm : (a) at 7 days; (b) 28 days; (b) at 90 days.

process lies in the hydration mechanism and are consistent with those of the activity index.

Fig. 10 shows a compact structure, and there are no significant differences in air void size and distribution between REFm, MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm at 7, 28 and 90 days. There is no micro-cracks effect on the surface of mortar specimens. The mortar specimen structure and the matrix between the aggregate are structurally intact.

Stereomicroscope observations through high-scale images (Fig. 14) were carried out to understand the initial microstructural characteristics of the mortar mixes containing DFW and MDFW < 63 μm examined. Fig. 11, obtained by stereomicroscopic analysis, shows that samples of REFm, MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm examined are heterogeneous. The cement is bright greyish. The structure of REFm, MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm reveals a porous material, with pores occasionally bigger than 1 mm. The fragments of aggregate do not differ in dimensions, colour and roundness. Quartz fragments (river aggregates) are of good roundness. Particulates of DFW are observed in the mortar mixes (Figs. 11b,

11c, 11e and 11 f). On the other hand, the contact regions are evident and allow for a global evaluation of the interaction between the materials. In REFm, MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm , a reaction layer is visible between the binder and each material (Fig. 12). Even at such low enlargement factors, it is possible to appreciate that the binder entered the materials' superficial porosity, ensuring good adhesion between the two. In the matrix of mortar mixes, no unreacted cement is observed.

4. Discussion

4.1. Physical properties

(i) Particle size distribution and fineness modulus: EN 13139 [35] specifies that an aggregate is considered a filler when the mass contents passing through the 2 mm, 0.125 mm, and 0.063 sieves are 100 %, 85–100 % and 70–100 %, respectively. The particle size distribution of the three specimens evaluated shows that DFW can be classified as a

Fig. 10. Digital images: (a) REFm at 7 days, (b) REFm at 28 days (c) REFm at 90 days; (d) MDFW at 7 days, (e) MDFW at 28 days (f) MDFW at 90 days (g) MDFW < 63 μm at 7 days (h) MDFW < 63 μm at 28 days (i) MDFW < 63 μm at 90 days. 40x40x160mm³ specimens.

Fig. 11. Stereomicroscope analysis: (a) REF M at 7 days; (b) M DFW at 7 days; (c) M DFW < 63 μm at 7 days; (d) REF M at 90 days; (e) M DFW at 90 days; (f) M DFW < 63 μm at 90 days. Black bar 1 mm.

Fig. 12. Stereomicroscope analysis: (a) REF M at 28 days; (b) M DFW at 28 days; (c) M DFW < 63 μm at 28 days.

filler according to EN 13139 [35]. Moreover, the particle size distribution indicates that DFW contains almost identical particles. This can limit the solid structure of mortar if DFW is used as a fine aggregate. Therefore, DFW will be a more promising filler material than a fine aggregate, based on its particle size distribution. On the other hand, the particle size distribution of the smaller fractions shows lower retention percentages than some cement or mineral admixtures [34, 47]. Generally, the literature reviewed does not indicate the presence of fibres or other contaminants in GFW [48] or from crushing quarry in BS [49] as in DFW under study. Sieving of samples or collecting in other parts of the manufacturing process may explain this. As mentioned in Section 1, stone fine waste may also contain other products derived from the transformation process. Mixtures such as lime, grit or particles derived from the progressive wear of the elements used in the cutting and polishing process have been reported [2].

The modulus of fineness varies from 4.40 to 6.20. These values are higher than those found in the literature for GFW as a replacement of sand in mortar, 1.02 and 1.48 [20, 26]. The above would again indicate that the most suitable use of DFW under study is as filler.

(ii) Shape, texture and colour: DFW's particles show an appropriate shape and texture for mortar use. It is known that flaky particles decrease the compressive strength of mortar, and a rough texture increases the adhesion of the cement paste. On the other hand, the angular shape of DFW can decrease the workability or increase the water

required for the same consistency in a conventional mortar when fine particles will be replaced with DFW, as is the case with granite and basalt powder [28, 50]. It is also expected that the diabase sludge's particles are more angular and prismatic than cement particles, which look rounder, as with GFW [25].

The fibres found in the fractions of DFW, over 475 μm , 212 μm , and 106 μm (Fig. 13b, c, d), may have an organic origin potentially stemming from the wooden pegs used during the squaring process (Fig. 13a). Despite their presence, these organic fibres are in minimal quantities, as indicated in Section 4.1, and should not adversely affect the setting or hardening of mortar containing this DFW. Dark slate particles also originate from the squaring process. The dimension stone factory *Villar del Rey Natural Stones S.L* also produces slate, although to a lesser extent. The squaring processing of slate blocks is made on the same processing line as the diabase stone, so eventual contamination of this slate rock fine is considered.

(iii) Specific density and specific surface area: As shown in Fig. 14a, the DFW's specific density, regardless of the fraction tested, is higher than that of GFW assessed by the helium pycnometer [1, 3, 34]. It is noted that these authors refer to density as specific gravity, specific mass, and specific gravity/specific density. The specific density of aggregate or filler is used to calculate quantities of cement-based material. The minerals and porosity of DFW influence this value. In this case, only porosity can explain the increase in density as the DFW

Fig. 13. Wood in DFW: (a) origin - wooden pegs; (b) wood fibres - over 475 μm ; (c) 475–212 μm fraction; (d) 212–106 μm fraction.

fraction decreases. The mineralogical composition, regardless of the type of fraction, is similar (Section 4.2). On the other hand, the DFW's specific density is close to that of cement [51]. This ensures the same volume of mortar for weight replacements. However, as the specific densities of DFW and cement are similar, the paste volume of DFW is similar to that of cement. Therefore, the lack of an increase in paste volume does not result in an increase in plasticity and cohesion, and consequently, there is no improvement in the workability of the mortar. This behaviour does not occur with mineral admixtures much lighter than cement, such as fly ash [52]. No BFW's density values evaluated by helium pycnometer were found in the literature. The literature review indicates specific gravity values for BFW of 2.9 and 2.99 but not the test method.

It is known that the surface area of a filler defines its reactivity. The increase in surface area is speculated to provide additional sites for the nucleation of hydration products, thereby accelerating the reactions. The DFW's specific surface may be higher than the specific surface area of GFW and pozzolans, such as fly ash, but slightly lower than waste, such as fired clay roof tiles and significantly lower than silica fume (Fig. 14b). Additionally, the specific surface area of DFW can exceed the 0.32–1.37 m^2/g range indicated for some types of cement [1, 27]. As the specific surface area of DFW is higher (or its particle size is finer) than that of cement particles, incorporating DFW may fill the voids between cement particles, improve the particle size distribution, and ultimately increase the packing density of cement-based materials. Consequently, the incorporation of DFW may reduce the water requirement of cement-based materials and enhance their compressive strength and durability, similar to the effects reported by Wang et al. [53] for limestone filler. However, this effect may be masked by increased water adsorption as the DFW's specific surface area (fineness) increases, specially at substitution levels above 5 %, as reported Aquel and Panesar [54] for the limestone filler. At a substitution level below 5 %, the mix is only influenced by the surface area of the cement. The increased water demand may decrease compressive strength, which the chemical effect may compensate if non-inert mineral admixtures are involved. In the case of DFW, its pozzolanic activity (Section 4.3) may compensate this effect. Moreover, the nature of DFW may also influence the water demand. Dimension diabase stone is slightly less porous than dimension granite stone [55]. Additives could also be a solution to decrease the amount of water demanded.

On the other hand, if DFW and cement particles have a similar specific surface area, DFW may not affect the water needs. Dobiszewska

et al. [23] indicated that using BFW as a cement replacement does not affect water demand to achieve normal consistency. Since BFW and cement particles had similar fineness, replacing cement with BFW did not significantly impact the specific surface area of the grains, which was the main reason normal consistency did not change with increased BFW content. It is known that cement with the highest specific surface area has higher initial strength. Possibly, these cements are the most suitable for the use of DFW, with a specific surface area of around 2.

Fine particles in DFW and DFW fraction < 25 μm explain that their surface areas are of the same order of magnitude.

(iv) Loose bulk density and water absorption: The DFW under study has loose bulk density values that are not higher than those of GFW, as stated by other researchers [3, 20, 50] (Figure 17). Bulk density clearly depends on how densely the particles are packed, and it follows that, for a material of a given specific density, it depends on the size distribution and shape of the particles: particles all of one size can be packed to a limited extent, but smaller particles can be added in the voids between the large ones, thus increasing the bulk density of the packed material [46]. This can explain why the bulk density value is lower despite the higher specific density of GFW. In addition, the presence of the fibres can create more voids due to the formation of microcavities in the interfacial transition zone between the cement paste and fibres [56]. On the other hand, the lower water absorption of DFW compared to GFW is in accordance with the properties of the dimension stone. Dimension diabase stone exhibits slightly less absorption and porosity than dimension granite stone [55].

4.2. Mineralogical composition

The mineralogical composition of the DFW under study does not align with the mineralogy typical of fresh diabase rock and the quarry, which includes plagioclase and pyroxene as essential components and biotite, magnetite, ilmenite, and apatite as accessory components. Instead, a significant presence of phyllosilicates (clay minerals) is revealed. These results are based on the findings of stereomicroscope analyses (Section 4.1). It is known that clay mineral fines can improve the plasticity or adherence of mortar but can also affect other properties, such as compressive strength. The presence of these minerals may be due to weathering or, more likely, to other local clay-bearing rocks. As explained in Section 4.1, the dimension stone factory *Villar del Rey Natural Stone S.L.* occasionally produces slate. The squaring processing of slate blocks is made on the same processing line as the dimension

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14. DFW/DFW fractions and different mineral admixtures: (a) specify density; (b) specific surface area.

diabase stone, so eventual contamination of this slate rock powder is considered. These findings justify the importance of a refined characterization of the stone fine waste before its use in mortars. Possible contaminations will affect the properties of DFW and, therefore, the properties of the mortar.

Generally, the minerals identified in DFW do not make any reactive contributions to the cement formulations. The presence of specific minerals containing heavy metals, such as Hg, Cd, Pb, or Cr, is not observed; therefore, it can be predicted that the release of hazardous components to the environment or human health must be very limited.

Direct observation, or the use of a scanner, of the mixing patterns of rock powders transformed at the site (diabase and slate) reveals a tonal variation that can serve as a preliminary visual indicator to evaluate the relative composition of the mixture found in DFW. This aspect will be useful for collection and sampling campaigns, given the variability of products likely to exist on-site. It is observed, however, that the ground

diabase (one of the fresh rocks transformed on site) has a relatively lighter and yellowish tone than would be expected. Therefore, it is necessary to consider some additional colour modification effects on the sludge in the case of prolonged environmental exposure. Therefore, in addition to the colour of the dry DFW, XRD was used to validate the proportion of diabase and slate. The comparative analysis of the XRD patterns, as described in Section 3.2, indicates a proportion of slate between 10 % and 20 %, but closer to the latter value.

Considering the factory's production history and sludge deposition, some compositional variability in the sludge is to be expected, but its global constituents will remain.

4.3. Chemical composition

As expected, Fig. 15 illustrates both similarities and differences between the chemical composition of the DFW under study and that

reported by other researchers for GFW [1, 3, 34, 57] and BFW [49, 22, 28, 58]. The mass fraction of SiO_2 in DFW is lower than that of GFW but within the BFW range. However, the mass fraction of Al_2O_3 in DFW is higher than that of GFW and BFW. In the case of Fe_2O_3 , it is within the basalt range of BFW. The mass fraction of Na_2O in DFW is higher than that of GFW and BFW. An important criterion closely related to the pozzolanic activity of SCM's is their acid chemistry: (a) $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 > 70\%$ and (b) high equivalent Na_2O content. Medina et al., 2017b reported in his study on GFW that, given its acidic chemistry and small particle size, this type of waste may, like natural pozzolans, exhibit some pozzolanic activity. By comparing the chemical compositions of DFW and GFW, the mass fractions of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ are somewhat lower in DFW than in GFW but have a similar Na_2O content. However, Al-Rawas et al. [59] and Chakchouk et al. [60] indicated that a total percentage of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 greater than 50 % is sufficient to produce good pozzolanic material. From this, the possible pozzolanic character of the diabase can be deduced, and, therefore, it is not an inert SCM. The chemical composition, however, cannot be used as the only criterion to determine the pozzolanic activity of pozzolanic materials [61].

On the other hand, the low presence of SO_3 indicates minimal sulphur content, suggesting that DFW will not cause mortar failure due to expansion from sulphur compounds. This differs from the potential expansion due to alkali-silica reactivity associated with some SiO_2 (~41.21 wt.) in DFW and (~41.21 wt.) in DFW < 25 μm bearing phases. Despite the presence of MgO and CaO in DFW, they are in a crystalline phase, preventing expansion from these phases. The mass fraction P_2O_5 of DFW is higher than that of GFW. P_2O_5 tends to form phosphoric acid, which can reduce the pH of the pore solution in pastes, negatively affecting cement hydration.

4.4. Pozzolanic activity

MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm exhibit at 28-day SAI's values greater than the 70 % requirement in European standard EN 450-1 [32] for cements with 25 % fly ash. These findings were similar to those reported by Medina et al. [30] for cements containing granite sludge waste

(~75 %) or by Davraz et al. [62] for andesite (76.5 %). The SAI of MDFW is similar to that of MDFW < 63 μm . However, the SAI of MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm at 90-days are 73 % and 77 %, respectively, lower than the 80 % requirement in European standard EN 450-1 [32] for cements with 25 % fly ash. As described in Section 3, MDFW shows similar SAI at 28 and 90 days of age. However, an increase in SAI with increasing age is observed in MDFW < 63 μm . The presence of organic fibres and curing in a humidity chamber may affect the hydration processes of mortars and, thus, the pozzolanic reactions in MDFW. It is known that organic material in certain proportions can affect the setting and hardening of cement-based materials. In addition, humidity has been able to dissolve the fibre compounds and act more effectively. MDFW < 63 μm does not reach 80 % of SAI required for pozzolanic materials such as fly ash. Mortar mixed with particle fraction of diabase sludge under 25 μm may show a higher activity index. Korkmaz [6] reported that the mechanical activation of fresh diabase causes a significant decrease in mineral particle size and an increase in the mineral-specific surface area. The particle size reduction from a maximum diameter of 57.51–19.33 and 10.89 μm increased the activity index at 28 days.

On the other hand, the increase in compressive strength from 7 days to 28 days of MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm is higher than that of REFM. This could result from pozzolanic reactions, which occur at later ages. It is known that the pozzolanic reactions are normally slower than the hydration of cement, and therefore, the strength of the pozzolan-cement mix is lower than that developed from mixed equivalents. The increase in compressive strength from 28 to 90 days of MDFW < 63 μm is slightly higher than that of REFM. Both MDFW and MDFW < 63 μm show pozzolanic activity in the first 28 days of the reaction. According to Frías et al. [63], the wastes evaluated in his study showed high pozzolanic activity in the first 28 days of reaction. In the case of MDFW, there is no increase from 28 to 90 days. As described above, the fibres may have affected the pozzolanic reaction.

The pozzolanic reaction refers to the reaction of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, forming C-S-H and C-A-H gel [64]. A qualitative review of the pattern revealed that the diffraction lines associated with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ were less intense in MRDW and MRDW < 63 μm than REFM at 7 days of the

Fig. 15. Chemical composition of GFW (Agrawal et al., 2021; Mashaly et al.; 2018; Nascimento et al., 2020; Ramadji et al., 2020) and BFW (Abdelaziz et al., 2014; Dobiszewska and Barnes, 2020; Dobiszewska and Beycioğlu, 2017; Uncik and Kmevcová, 2013).

curing stage. However, at 28 days, the Ca(OH)_2 peak was somewhat similar for MDFW and $\text{MDFW} < 63 \mu\text{m}$, indicating that most Ca(OH)_2 has been consumed to form an additional C–S–H phase. That behaviour can be related to the pozzolanicity patterns of granite sludge [29, 65]. This type of low-early-age activity additions initially acted as fillers, providing nucleation sites and increasing the space available for hydration product precipitation. At later ages, this filler effect was superseded by the pozzolanic effect, reducing the portlandite content and, consequently, of the C–H–S released. At 90 days, Ca(OH)_2 was not sufficiently available to fully react with the dissolved silicates of DFW or $\text{DFW} < 63 \mu\text{m}$ [66] or the presence of calcium carbonate deriving from portlandite carbonation by atmospheric CO_2 ($\text{Ca(OH)}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3$) during sample curing.

The new addition of mineral admixtures (DFW or $\text{DFW} < 63 \mu\text{m}$) induces no changes in the microstructure or any significant effect. Granite shows similar behaviour. Medina et al. (2017b) reported that partial replacement of cement GFW has no adverse effect on matrix uniformity. Moreover, GFW exhibited no mineralogical changes in the cement hydration products, unlike other types of waste with similar mineralogy, such as mining waste [67] or calcined paper sludge [68].

5. Conclusions

Technical remarks, characterization findings and benefits for industry were drawn from different stages of this study. A new fine waste from the dimension stone sector has been identified for use in mortar. This fine stone waste is generated during the production process of dimension diabase. This stone is present on five continents. It is part of the stone known commercially as *black granites* (basalt, diabase, gabbro, diorite and anorthosite). However, the chemical and mineralogical compositions of such rock are quite different from those of true granites.

The characterisation has highlighted the need for detailed characterization studies of this type of waste to disclose some quality control parameters under real application conditions. Factors that may affect its variability, such as the stages and processes where it was generated, must be considered.

The DFW under study can be considered a filler material due to its size distribution and modulus of fineness; therefore, it can be used as a replacement for cement in mortars due to the filler and nucleation effect. The DFW particles have a shape and texture suitable for their use in mortar mixes, although they contain wood fibres (1 %) and particles from the slate rock (20 %) in their composition. The DFW's specific density is close to that of some cements. This ensures the same volume of mortar for mass replacements, although the workability of mortar can decrease. The DFW's specific surface is higher than that of some cements, which may increase the packing density. A higher specific surface may increase water adsorption and decrease the workability and compressive strength. However, dimension diabase stone and DFW have lower absorption than other rocks and wastes, such as granite, and may compensate for this effect. The minerals identified and the chemical composition of DFW do not interfere with the cement formulations. The DFW under study cannot be considered a pozzolan. Its SAI satisfies the requirement in EN 450–1 at 90 days. However, this filler is not inert because it has pozzolanic activity, which can increase the ratios of cement replacement in relation to other wastes. According to these results, the DFW under study reveals its potential as a filler material in mortar production. Further research is warranted to optimize its incorporation into cement formulations and to assess its long-term performance.

The use of DFW can generate benefits for two industrial sectors: i) The dimension stone sector can reduce the costs associated with managing this waste and its environmental impact; ii) DFW is a waste that does not require crushing and sieving processes. This leads to cost savings compared to other wastes and cheap raw materials. Furthermore, DFW can be used as a filler to replace cement. Therefore, the mortar sector industry can reduce energy consumption, decrease reliance on

non-renewable resources, and enhance cost-effectiveness compared to cement.

In any case, these industrial benefits imply the investigation of solutions that ensure the homogeneity of DFW. Designing DFW management processes in dimension diabase factories and production controls similar to those established in crushed-aggregate quarries can be some of the solutions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pacheco-Menor Maria Concepcion: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Pereira Manuel Francisco Costa:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jorge de Brito:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision. **Inês Flores-Colen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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